

Mobile Bio-Fertiliser Solutions

Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

D7.10

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

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NOMAD in a nutshell

Organic waste represents a high percentage of global waste composition with an average of 46% worldwide. In the EU, 1.4 billion tonnes of manure are produced each year however, estimates suggest that less than 10% is currently actively managed. Resulting GHG emissions pose a serious climate change threat. Additionally, rural areas face challenges to coordinate their waste management due to poor infrastructure.

The NOMAD project aims to recover valuable renewable energy and nutrients from multiple organic waste streams producing high-quality organic fertiliser from biogas digestate. NOMAD will bring experienced EU and Chinese partners to develop a disruptive model that aims to deliver a complete, localised, circular solution for digestate utilization. The plan is to build a prototype plant for this transformation process and integrate it on a trailer so that it is easily transportable on the road. Once the prototype has been built and tested in the UK, the trailer will be moved to Greece, Italy and Malta to be applied at different demo-sites with very different types of organic waste. The four demo-sites of NOMAD feature specific digestate types (UK: food waste; Greece: animal residue and manure; Italy: crop waste; Malta: municipal wastewater) to analyse issues and regulatory bottlenecks arising and assess the solution.

NOMADs goal is to support a vibrant organic circular economy model that can be replicated widely across rural, peri-urban and eventually, urban areas. It will expand circular enterprise opportunities by diversifying the range of organic products that can be derived from digestate as well as exploring how digestate can be combined with other organic waste by-products to increase the value of all inputs. In doing so, it will generate jobs and training opportunities to enhance rural livelihoods and strengthen sustainable agricultural practices through greater resource efficiency and reduced reliance on non-renewable resources. At the heart of the project lies the critical collaboration between EU and Chinese research and technical partners in co-designing an innovative approach to digestate valorisation.

Executive Summary

The 'Final Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Monitoring' deliverable D7.10 provides a comprehensive overview of the project's communication efforts, dissemination activities, stakeholder engagement, and outreach actions.

The document briefly explains the project's visual identity and templates, including the development of visual elements and guidelines for consistent branding. It also presents communication materials such as brochures, roll-ups, PowerPoint presentations, and infographics that effectively communicate the project's goals.

Conducted communication activities such as press releases, journalistic articles, and project videos are presented and linked. Dissemination activities that included scientific publications, event participation, and organization and final project conference are detailed.

Stakeholder engagement in the demo countries (UK, Greece, Italy, and Malta) is summarized, highlighting strategies to engage government agencies, industry representatives, and local communities.

Statistics on the project's website and social media channels provide insight into the online presence and effectiveness of its strategies, including visits, engagement, followers, and views.

Chinese partners' outreach efforts in China, such as events, press appearances, brochures, stakeholder engagement, and scientific publications, are also presented.

Disclaimer

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Table of Contents

1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	1
1.1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY PLAN	1
1.2. PROJECT BRANDING	1
1.2.1. VISUAL IDENTITY	1
1.2.2. TEMPLATES	1
2. COMMUNICATION MATERIAL	2
2.1. PROJECT BROCHURE	2
2.2. ROLL-UP	2
2.3. CORPORATE POWERPOINT PRESENTATION	2
2.4. INFOGRAPHICS	3
3. COMMUNICATION ACTIONS	4
3.1. PRESS RELEASES	4
3.2. JOURNALISTIC ARTICLES & INTERVIEWS	4
3.3. PROJECT VIDEOS	5
4. DISSEMINATION ACTIONS	7
4.1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS AND PRESENTATIONS	7
4.2. EVENTS	9
4.3. FINAL NOMAD CONFERENCE	11
5. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	14
6. ONLINE OUTREACH	8
6.1. WEBSITE	8
6.2. SOCIAL NETWORKS	9
7. OUTREACH IN CHINA	10
7.1. EVENT PARTICIPATION	10
7.2. EVENT HOSTING	11
7.3. NEWS OUTREACH	12
7.4. DIGITAL MEDIA	13
7.5. BROCHURE	13
7.6. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	13
7.7. DISSEMINATION – SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION	14
8. CONCLUSION	15

1. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

1.1. Communication and Dissemination Strategy Plan

Within the first three month of the project ESCI developed the ‘Communication and Dissemination Strategy Plans’ (D7.2 & D7.3) that established a framework for all communication and dissemination activity done in the NOMAD project. Based on the results of the M12 and M24 version of the “Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring (D7.8) the deliverables D7.2 & D7.3 were updated in M12 and M24.

1.2. Project Branding

1.2.1. Visual Identity

In M1 the project’s visual identity was developed. A logo (Figure 1) including an icon and a subline was designed and coordinated with the NOMAD consortium during the Kick-off meeting and a subsequent online voting. A colour palette (Figure 1) and specific fonts were defined to give all communication materials a uniform look with high recognition value.

Figure 1 NOMAD logo and colour palette

1.2.2. Templates

Templates to give all official documents (public or confidential) a uniform look were developed in M1 and distributed to all NOMAD partners.

Figure 2 - NOMAD Microsoft Word and PowerPoint templates

2. Communication material

2.1. Project Brochure

The project brochure in English (Figure 3) was produced as a PDF version in M6 and distributed among partners. Translations have been done into Maltese, Greek and Italian. The digital version is downloadable from the project website. Printed versions in Maltese, Greek, Italian and English were supplied to partners, according to demand, in M21. This delay in printing was due to the global pandemic and the shift from in person events, during which brochures are normally handed out, to the mostly online formats.

Figure 3 - Brochure; English version (left), Greek version (greek)

2.2. Roll-Up

To accompany the first large event participation in M33 by the UK partners a Roll-Up (Figure 4) was designed. It gives a project overview using one of the infographics and creates awareness by having the main topics of the projects in bullets.

Figure 4 – Roll-Up

2.3. Corporate PowerPoint Presentation

A corporate PowerPoint presentation (PPT) in English (Figure 5) was produced in M6 and made available for all partners via the file sharing platform used in the NOMAD project. Through this PPT partners will be able to easily present general information (i.e., goals, activities and expected results) about the NOMAD project while speaking at events or meeting while being able to complement the presentation with more detailed information concerning the presented topic.

Figure 5 - Corporate PowerPoint Presentation; selected slides

2.4. Infographics

In the fast-paced digital world with a multitude of channels to communicate about the project, to catch someone’s attention quickly is of key importance. Graphical elements and iconography are a successful way to achieve this. Therefore, eye-catching icons have been created to visualize key concepts and technologies (Figure 6) and help structure the NOMAD project.

Figure 6 - Icons for the field trials, truck, and selected technologies

From those, two overview graphics (Figure 7) were designed to help illustrate the idea behind the NOMAD project.

Figure 7 - Overview infographics

Additionally, some questions and topics surrounding digestate and fertiliser use were visualized to explain the background behind the NOMAD project (Figure 8).

Figure 8 - Topic related infographics

Furthermore, the inside of the two NOMAD trailers was visualized in a simplified way (Figure 9) and the set-up of the field growing trials was visualized (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - NOMAD trailer structure

Figure 9 - NOMAD field trial set-up

3. Communication actions

3.1. Press releases

Since the beginning of the project partners have been actively communicating about the launch of the project on- and offline, i.e., through their own website, social networks, or other channels. One means of communication action especially in the beginning to make the project know or at milestones during the project is through press releases distributed on websites and newsletters (Table 1).

Table 1 - Overview of press releases on NOMAD

Title	Location	Partner	Date
"CluBE, CERTH, DIADYMA and MATESION participated and co-organized the kick-off meeting of the new project NOMAD"	CluBE website	CLuBE	November 2019
Scientists develop a truck to produce bio-fertiliser	AlphaGalileo.org; NOMAD website; NOMAD LinkedIn channel	ESCI	December 2019
Scientists develop a truck to produce bio-fertiliser	Stopford Website	Stopford (SEE)	December 2019

3.2. Journalistic articles & interviews

A total of ten journalistic articles were published in print and online newspapers. A mixture of international and local publications was targeted to reach a variety of stakeholders and general public. An overview of date, title and publication place (with link, if published online) can be found in table 2.

Next to journalistic articles, there have been several written, as well as video interviews with NOMAD partners. An overview can be found in table 3.

Table 2 – Overview journalistic articles

Date	Title	Publication Place
M10	Converting waste into a usable resource	Project website
M21	Meet the NOMAD – mobile digestate treatment	AD & BIORESOURCES News – Issue 51
M32	Unearthing Digestate with NOMAD	AWE Magazine – Issue 74
M32	A rural renaissance: How EU research is breathing new life into rural areas	Rural Connections Magazine (ENRD) – Issue 1/2022
M40	Anaerobic digestion to tackle antibiotic resistance	resource.co
M41	NOMAD: Project to promote good circular economy practices using a mobile biofertilizer production unit (in Greek)	ptolemeos.gr + printed
M43	A "prefecture" that does "green" waste management on site (in Greek)	Dikailogitika
M45	NOMAD: An EU Project for Sustainable Agriculture Development	Earth.org
M45	Biofertilizzanti da digestato: un progetto europeo per l'agricoltura sostenibile (in Italian)	RecoverWeb.it
M45	Pilot trials to mobilise digestate processing	Agriconnect.com – Volume 46, Issue 7, page 36

Table 3 - Overview interviews

Date	Partner	Type & Location
M38	CERTH / CLUBE / DIADYMA	Video interview with Regional Governor of Western Macedonia – YouTube channel
M44	DIADYMA	Revitalizing Soil and Transforming the Local Economy: Approach to Post-Lignite Land Restoration project website
M44	UNIFI	From Soil Degradation to Soil Regeneration: Enhancing European Agriculture project website
M45	IHE Delft	Combating antibiotic resistance: The important role of antibiotic removal in waste treatment project website
M45	LEAP	NOMAD: Revolutionizing Digestate Management and Enabling Circular Bio-Economies project website
M45	LEAP	Building the Future: Engineering Trailers for Advanced Digestate Processing project website

3.3. Project Videos

In total seven project videos were produced. Six of them were published on YouTube and LinkedIn as well as embedded on the project website. One video (a video news release, VNR in short) was broadcasted via the European Broadcasting Union (EBU), to additionally reach public service media worldwide.

Italian, Maltese and Greek subtitles were added to the introductory and final project video. Demo site videos were produced in English, a dubbed version with their local language will be published in July/August 2023.

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

An overview with publication date, title, link and views can be found in table 4. Unfortunately, due to many delays in the project the larger portion of the videos could only be produced in the last few months of the project, therefore view numbers, especially for the last two videos released are not that high. The videos will be available at least 5 years after project end and it is expected that more views will accumulate.

Table 4 - Overview project videos

Date	Title	Views (30.06.2023)*
M15	<u>On the Road to a Circular Bioeconomy! A New Mobile Digestate Processing Solution</u> - Introductory video -	1838
M43	<u>Digestate - A Source for Green Energy, Irrigation Water and Nutrients</u> - Greek demo video -	890
M44	<u>Empowering Malta's Farmers and Protecting Groundwater Resources</u> - Maltese demo video -	1698
M44	Tackling the antibiotics problem at its root: Mobile digestate treatment (video news release)	Broadcasted via EBU on May 16 th 2023**
M45	<u>Sustainable Farming – Organic Fertiliser From Biogas Plant Residue</u> - Italian demo video - Release Date: 22.06.23	581
M45	<u>Mobile Organic Fertiliser Production – Local Solution for Biogas Plant Residue</u> - Final project video - Release Date: 27.06.23	334
M45	<u>Building Mobile Units to Process Waste of Anaerobic Digestion Plants</u> - UK demo video - Release Date: 29.06.23	57

* YouTube & LinkedIn views

** A report from the EBU shows, that the following companies have picked up the distribution of our NOMAD VNR. This is however not a guarantee that they used the material in a report or similar:

- ESFORT – Forta
- ESCCT - Corporació Catalana de Mitjans Audiovisuals, SA
- JPSPTV - Sky Perfect JSAT Corporation
- AUABC - Australian Broadcasting Corporation
- CACBC - Canadian Broadcasting Corporation
- ITFAO - Food And Agriculture Organization Of The United Nations

4. Dissemination actions

4.1. Scientific publications and presentations

As results are just becoming available at projects end, presentation of the results in scientific publications or events were not that abundant in the project lifetime (table 5). For an overview of planned publications see deliverable D7.4.

Table 5 - Overview scientific dissemination

Date	Author	Title	Type	Event
M1	UCL	-	Conference presentation	University of Surrey Biogas Conference
M13	UCL	-	Conference presentation	LCA Food conference
M14	UCL	-	Conference presentation	Westminster Food & Nutrition Forum policy conference
M20	Lin et al.	Using LCA to Support the Development of Novel Mobile Nutrient Recovery Technology From Anaerobic Digestion	Conference talk	SETAC Europe 2021
M20	Black et al.	Life Cycle Assessment of Anaerobic Digestion Biofertiliser Value Chains - How Methodological Choices Impact LCA Outcomes	Conference poster	SETAC Europe 2021
M21	Proskynitopoulou et al.	ΒΙΩΣΙΜΗ ΕΚΜΕΤΑΛΛΕΥΣΗ ΤΟΥ ΥΠΟΛΕΙΜΜΑΤΟΣ ΤΗΣ ΜΟΝΑΔΑΣ ΒΙΟΑΕΡΙΟΥ ΣΤΟ ΠΛΑΙΣΙΟ ΤΗΣ ΚΥΚΛΙΚΗΣ ΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΑΣ: ΠΑΡΑΓΩΓΗ ΟΡΓΑΝΙΚΩΝ ΛΙΠΑΣΜΑΤΩΝ ΥΨΗΛΗΣ ΠΟΙΟΤΗΤΑΣ	Conference presentation	13th Panhellenic Scientific Conference on Chemical Engineering
M21	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Sustainable exploitation of biogas plant digestate within circular economy: high quality organic fertilizer production	Conference presentation	9th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management
M22	Proskynitopoulou et al.	SUSTAINABLE EXPLOITATION OF BIOGAS PLANT DIGESTATE FOR THE PRODUCTION OF HIGH-QUALITY PRODUCTS USING SELECTIVE ELECTRODIALYSIS	Conference presentation and publication in Environmental sciences proceedings (https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2022021075)	5th EWaS (Efficient Water Systems) International Conference
M22	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Anaerobic digestate exploitation from biogas plants originated in Western Macedonia	Conference poster	INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM AND WORKSHOPS SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS AT TIMES OF TRANSITION (SuST)

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

M24	Proskynitopoulou et al	Simultaneous nutrient ions recovery from anaerobic digestates of different origin by using Selective Electrodialysis	Conference presentation	9th ICGC
M25	Moradi et al.	Pharmaceutical Removal from Food-processing Digestate	Conference poster	Collaborative Water Resource Management for a Water Secure World
M41	Sakellariou et al.	Utilisation of residues from biogas plants of Western Macedonia - Preliminary study (in Greek)	Conference poster	1st Conference and Fair - Western Macedonia Innovation Days
M42	Lin et al.	-	Conference poster	2nd BBNet Conference - BBNet
M45	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Anaerobic digestate exploitation from biogas plants originated in Western Macedonia	Conference poster	31 st EUBCE 2023
M45	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Treatment of anaerobically digested pig manure with membrane processes for nutrient recovery and antibiotics removal	Conference presentation	10th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management
After project end	Proskynitopoulou et al.		Scientific publication	Environmental Science and Pollution Research (<i>Submitted, Under Review</i>)
After project end	Verdi et al.	Improved digestate for sustainable fertilization: preliminary results of NOMAD project	Conference poster	52° National Congress of Italian Society of Agronomy (Naples, 25-27 September 2023)
After project end	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Mobile solution for digestate transformation to high added-value products	Conference presentation	26th Conference Process Integration, Modelling and Optimisation for Energy Saving and Pollution Reduction (Thessaloniki, 8-11 October 2023)
After project end	Moradi et al.	Practical application of UVOX Redox® for pharmaceutical removal from liquid digestate in two biogas plants	Scientific publication	Environmental Technology & Innovation (<i>Submitted, Under Review</i>)
After project end	Lin et al.	Using LCA to Support the Development of Novel Mobile Nutrient Recovery Technology From Anaerobic Digestion	Scientific publication	TBD
After project end	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Treatment of anaerobically digested pig manure by applying membrane processes for nutrient recovery and antibiotics removal	Scientific publication	Environmental Technology & Innovation (<i>Submitted, Under Review</i>)
After project end	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Turning biogas digestate from municipal sewage sludge into nutrients and clean water	Scientific publication	Water Research (<i>Submitted, under review</i>)
After project end	Proskynitopoulou et al.	Nutrient recovery from digestate: pilot test experiments	Scientific publication	Journal of Environmental Management (<i>Submitted, under review</i>)

4.2. Events

Apart from participation in scientific conferences partners were busy organizing and participating in targeted trainings, educational events and more general outreach events (table 6).

Table 6 - Overview of event participation of NOMAD partners

Date	Partner	Contribution	Location	Event title	Metrics
M1	UCL	Participation	Surrey, UK	University of Surrey Biogas Conference	<200 participants
M4	LEAP	Exhibition stand	Nantes, France	Biogaz Europe 2020	n.a.
M5	UCL	Presentation	Bahrain	UK-Bahrain Waste management Symposium	<200 participants
M6	UCL	Presentation	Goiânia, Brazil	British Council Newton Waste-Water-Energy-Food Nexus Workshop	<100 participants
M8	ANCI Lazio	Presentation	Online	IUC webinar	30 participants
M11	UCL	Participation	Online	ADBA event: Introduction to AD: Benefits, value and role in the Green Recovery	<100 participants
M13	DIADYMA	Presentation	Online	Interreg ADRION: Matchmaking event on bioeconomy applications. Waste valorisation in a circular bioeconomy process	44 registrations
M15	CluBE	Presentation	Online	Sustainable use of Soil Production and Degradation of Bio-based products, Greek BioEconomy Forum	170 participants
M15	CluBE	Presentation	Online	Biomass Day 2020 – Bioeconomy &	147 participants

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

				Bioenergy Forum 2020	
M17	UCL	Participation	Online	EAB event: Biogas – the next wave	<200 participants
M18	UCL	Participation	Online	WBA Report Launch	<200 participants
M18	CluBE, DIADYMA	Participation	Hybrid (DIADYMA's office, Greece)	Meeting with Hellenic Association of Biogas (HABIO) and Hellenic Biomass Association	>10 participants
M18	UNIFI	Presentation	Online	Seminars for Tuscan farmers (Dal Campo alla tavola: grani antichi bio della Val d'Orcia)	20 participants
M20	UCL	Conference talk & poster	Online	SETAC Europe 2021	<2000 visitors
M22	Stopford	Presentation	UK	Meeting with National Farmer's Union (NFU)	n.a.
M24	ANCI Lazio	Organization	Ventotene, Italy	Training Camp 2021 Ventotene	63 participants
M25	UCL, LEAP, Stopford	Presentation + panel discussion	Online	Countryside COP	<1000 participants
M26	ANCI Lazio	Nomination+ Participation	Online	2021 Award of Excellence "towards a circular economy" Italian prize	10 participants + online audience
M32	ATRIGA, CERTH	Exhibition booth	Ta' Qali, Malta	Malta AgriFair	n.a.
M33	UCL, LEAP, Stopford	Exhibition booth	Cambridgeshire, UK	CEREALS	<600 visitors
M33	CERTH, CluBE	Workshop	Kozani, Greece	Climate Neutral Week	>20 participants
M37	UNIFI	Presentation	Sevilla, Spain	Seminar for PhD students of Department of Agronomy of University of Sevilla (Circular economy at the farm level: The	10 participants

				importance of reclaiming resources)	
M37	CluBE, CERTH, DIADYMA	Presentation + NOMAD truck showcase	Thessaloniki, Greece	29 th Agrotica 2022	>3000 participants
M41	UCL	Conference talk & poster	Harrogate, UK	2nd BBnet conference: "Green Future" What's next for biorefineries?	<200 visitors
M41	CluBE, CERTH	Exhibition booth	Kozani, Greece	1st Conference and Fair - Western Macedonia Innovation Days	<1.500 participants
M42	CluBE	Exhibition booth	Athens, Greece	5th International fair Title : Environmental technologies - Verde.tec	>5000 participants
M43	CERTH	Public Talk + Poster	Thessaloniki, Greece	WIRE Thessaloniki Workshop	60 participants
M43	ANCI Lazio	Public Talk + Exhibition booth	Rome, Italy	Festival of creative recycling "Riscarti 10"	791 visitors of the booth
M45	ANCI Lazio	Workshop	Online	EU Green Week Event "Recupero nutrient e HOOP bioeconomy"	60 participants

Approach to participants of different relevant projects addressing issues of soil health and circular economy has been achieved also through the Mission Soil events.

In addition to the above a number of projects that are relevant to the NOMAD project has been identified and communication with some of the participating partners has been established.

Table 7. Relevant projects.

Project	Coordinator	End	Status of contact
WainUT	FUNDACION CARTIF	2026	Follow-up activity
NUTRIMAN	3R-BioPhosphate Ltd.	2021	Follow-up activity
SYSTEMIC	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	2021	
ULTIMATE	KWR WATER BV	2024	
NextGen	KWR WATER BV	2022	
WIDER UPTAKE	SINTEF AS	2024	

FERTIMANURE	FUNDACIO UNIVERSITARIA BARMES	2023	Follow-up activity
HYDROUSA	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	2023	
NanoPhosTox	KEEMILISE JA BIOLOOGILISE FUUSIKA INSTITUUT	2024	
RUN4LIFE	FCC AQUALIA SA	2021	
MEIoDIZER	POLITECNICO DI TORINO	2026	
RUSTICA	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	2024	
LEX4BIO	LUONNONVARAKESKUS	2024	
P2GreeN	AGRATHAER GMBH	2026	
REFLOW	UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK	2023	
E-motion	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	2022	
CAFE	ECOLE NATIONALE DES PONTS ET CHAUSSEES	2025	
NewFert	FERTIBERIA SA	2018	
reNEW	UTB ENVIROTEC KORNYEZETTECHNOLOGIAIZART KORUEN MUKODO RT	2016	
MINAGRIS	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	2026	Follow-up activity
WATERAGRI	LUNDS UNIVERSITET	2024	Follow-up activity
Circular Agronomics	INSTITUT DE RECERCA I TECNOLOGIA AGROALIMENTARIES	2023	Follow-up activity
FER-PLAY	ASOCIACION EMPRESARIAL CENTRO TECNOLOGICO DE LA ENERGIA Y DEL MEDIO AMBIENTE DE LA REGION DE MURCIA	2025	
VALUEWASTE	CETENMA	2022	Follow-up activity

4.3. Final NOMAD conference

Figure 11 - Final conference graphic

The final project conference “Transformation of Europe’s agriculture: A mobile technology solution for turning AD digestate to fertilizers and soil amenders” was hosted on April 27th 2023 by partner UCL at the University College London. The event witnessed a turnout of 43 attendees from six different countries, reflecting the international significance of NOMAD’s mission. The program included keynote speeches from external experts (table 7) on the topic of various aspects of anaerobic digestate (AD) and organic waste management, a panel discussion with external and project experts, and presentations of

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

several NOMAD partners on progress and achievements surrounding the design & built process, nutrient recovery and field growing trails as well as the Life Cycle Assessment.

Table 8 - External experts

Name	Affiliation
Charlotte Morton	Chief Executive of the Anaerobic Digestion and Bioresources Association of the UK (ADBA), UK
Dr. Anastasios Zouboulis	Professor of Chemical and Environmental Technology at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece
Dr. Dimitra Lambropoulou	Associate Professor of Environmental Chemistry at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece
Dr. Laura Cardenas	Rothamsted Research, UK
David Tompkins	AquaEnviro, UK
Dr. Panagiotis Kougias	Head of Waste Management and Bioprocessing Laboratory at DIMITRA, Greece
Angela Bywater	EbNet Network Manager at University of Southampton & Methanogen UK Ltd, UK

Figure 12 - Pictures from final conference

Figure 13 - Pictures from final conference (left: panel discussion)

5. Stakeholder engagement

Activity T7.6 Stakeholder engagement had 2 main components: the development of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan and the preparation and monitoring of the Stakeholder workshops.

The Stakeholder Engagement Plan (D7.6) was prepared in the first 6 months of the project as a methodology for identifying stakeholders in the entire ecosystem of digestate production and mapping their interest, decision and investment power (Figure 14). Furthermore, the document has been guiding pilot partners from UK, Malta, Italy and Greece in understanding which the specific challenges are associated with stakeholders' engagement (SE) and which are the specific approaches for an effective engagement, based on target groups' interests and expectations associated with the NOMAD project.

Figure 14 . NOMAD stakeholder mapping

Last but not least, the SE Plan has made correlations between stakeholder engagement and the content needed for advancing project activities, in order to inform WP and task leaders on when the SE process should be more intensive and also on which are the key stakeholders to count on at that particular moment (figure 15). D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Plan was developed by PP6 US with strong support from PP11 ESCI and PP12 SEE and it was developed in parallel and in synergy with D2.2 Stakeholder requirements, including local variations, in order to assure an integrated approach at project level. Periodically telco meetings were organized with both partners in order to define a common approach for both deliverables.

Figure 15 - NOMAD project timeline according to the stakeholder/task matrix

During this period, a comprehensive list of stakeholders was defined, the logic for their involvement during the project duration was established and the stakeholder hierarchy was made. At the beginning of March 2020, all project partners (with emphasis on WP/task leaders) were invited by Urbasofia to contribute with content on the Stakeholder Engagement Plan. As such, they provided contributions for the following: the level of influence/interest of each stakeholder category in key stages of the project, the possible risks associated with the engagement process in each phase and also on key words for Communication and Dissemination Materials. Furthermore, PP11 ESCI was invited to contribute with general and specific ideas of Communication and Dissemination materials which could support the Engagement Process (figure 16).

Key Stakeholder Type	Interests and expectations	WPs/Tasks of Interest	Possible involvement	Engagement mechanisms
Public (regional and local authorities)	- Provide the necessary services and regulations for the wellbeing of citizens and assure a clean and safe environment;	WP2 (T2.2, T2.6) WP5 (T5.5) WP6 (T6.2, T6.5, T6.6)	-Identification of stakeholders in the respective pilot areas; -Provide feedback regarding the overall goals and outputs of	Formal meetings Interviews Workshops and conferences Field trips

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

	- Develop better strategies and regulations for soil management, environment protection and resource efficiency;	WP7 (T7.5, T7.6)	the project; -Provide local/regional data; - Provide requirements and development needs to be addressed in workshops - Contribute at modelling tool definition with feedback and ideas; - Contribute to policy formulation;	Newsletters Web communication via social media
Food security institutions	- Providing better regulations for assuring healthy food production and supply, equitable access to food, food supply stability; - Developing effective frameworks for food security policies;	WP2 (T2.2, T2.5, T2.6, T2.7) WP3 (T3.7) WP4 (T4.6) WP5 (T5.5) WP6 (T6.5, T6.6) WP7 (T7.5, T7.6)	- Provide legislative limitations and potential risks and barriers in developing the product; - Provide concerns regarding the security of the organic product; - Contribute at modelling tool definition with feedback and ideas; -Contribute to policy and regulations formulation; -Provide requirements to be addressed during the workshops;	Formal meetings Interviews Focus groups Workshops and conferences Newsletters Web communication via social media
Environment authorities	-Assure that all the activities undertaken in the pilot areas don't harm the environment; - Develop effective frameworks for	WP2 (T2.2, T2.5, T2.6, T2.7) WP3 (T3.7) WP4 T4.7)	- Provide legislative limitations and potential risks and barriers in developing the product; - Provide concerns regarding the environmental	Formal meetings Workshops and conferences Field trips Newsletters

	environment protection policies and regulations;	WP5 (T5.4,T5.5) WP6 (T6.5, T6.6) WP7 (T7.5, T7.6)	security of the product; - Provide local/regional data; - Contribute at modelling tool definition with feedback and ideas; -Contribute to policy and regulations formulation;	Web communication via social media
Quality Standard Agencies	-High standard working environments for product development (according to national/EU standards);	WP2 (T2.2, T2.3, T2.4, T2.5, T2.6) WP3 (T3.1, T3.7) WP4 (T4.1, T4.2, T4.6, T4.8) WP5 (T5.4,T5.5) WP6 (T6.5, T6.6) WP7 (T7.6)	-Provide concerns regarding the working environment for product development; -Provide feedback for the final product; -Contribute with ideas for policy and regulations formulation;	Workshops and conferences Field trips Newsletters Web communication via social media
Farmers/Farmers Associations	-Lower costs and higher productivity for food production; -Healthy and safe solutions for food production; -Accredited products for food production; -More inclusive policies and regulations for food production;	WP2 (T2.2, T2.5, T2.6, T2.7) WP5 (T5.4,T5.5) WP6 (T6.2, T6.3, T6.5, T6.6) WP7 (T7.5, T7.6)	-Provide ideas and needs regarding the circular bioeconomy model and the product itself; -Provide requirements to be addressed during the workshops; - Contribute at modelling tool definition with feedback and ideas; -Provide past personal experiences with organic fertilizers;	Interviews Questionnaires Workshops and conferences Focus groups Field trips Newsletters Web communication via social media

Figure 16 - Stakeholder involvement and engagement activities

Based on the take-aways from the Stakeholder Engagement Plan, the preparation of Stakeholder Workshops in each pilot country (IT, GR, MT, UK) was initiated in M13. Initially, pilot partners were requested to prepare a comprehensive list of stakeholders (based on the predefined categories in the SE Plan) and to constantly update it during the engagement process. Furthermore, PP6 has started framing the format of the 3 envisioned workshops (topic, period, main objectives, target groups, foreseen outcomes,

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

speakers, visual materials etc) together with the WP7 leader and with the responsible partners in all the 4 contexts. The topics envisioned for the workshops were the following:

- First module: Theoretical information on circular bio-economy concept and its socio-economic benefits + presentation of the NOMAD product and the (local/regional) status quo of the project
- Second module: Scenarios for embedding the NOMAD product in the local rural economy & defining the policy framework
- Third module: Presentation on the final product & overview of the development process

PP6 Urbasofia has organized calls with each national cluster of partners in order to understand the specific local/national requirements and to adapt the Stakeholder Workshop format to the local/national needs and expectations. The responsible partners were asked to bring their contributions in regard to the specific subjects to be addressed (besides the general topic of the module) and the main outcomes they want to achieve as a result of the workshops.

Even if initially foreseen for spring/early summer 2021, due to the prolonged pandemics restrictions it was decided at consortium level that physical workshops were postponed until they could be held in safe conditions. Furthermore, it was decided at consortium level that project partners are allowed to join external fairs and conferences for assuring the envisioned engagement, as the pandemics had a massive negative impact on people participation in both virtual and physical events. Thus, it was agreed that NOMAD partners would reach a considerably bigger number of relevant stakeholders by organizing at least 2 dedicated NOMAD sessions as part of bigger (physical or online) events, than by organizing their own workshops. In this alternative scenario, the content of the workshops also became more flexible and project partners adapted their presentations and interactive sessions to the audience present at the conferences.

In this context, PP6 US has developed a set of materials meant to support pilot partners in both scenarios (physical/virtual):

- one concerning targeted content for different types of stakeholders (measurable results of interaction with stakeholders, questions/exercices to be held in order to achieve those results, topics to be presented, envisioned number of participants from each category, etc)
- the second concerning specific event - in this sense, partners were asked to list local/regional events related to NOMAD, best practices considered of interest for specific types of users, social media channels where those stakeholders could be reached, etc)

Additionally, regular coordination through telco meetings with each pilot team, as well as additional preparatory materials such as online and physical surveys templates, online registration forms and invitations were provided by PP6 US. Partners were advised to update the scenarios templates provided by US regarding target audience, envisioned outputs and key questions to be asked in order to reach the outputs.

Stakeholder Engagement in UK

Starting from the content in the templates, UK organized their first stakeholder workshop on the 11th of October 2021, as part of Countryside COP, entitled NOMAD: Mobile digestate management – Supporting the Future of Sustainable Farming. In this regard,

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

regular telco meetings (once a week) were organized between UK partners, US and ESCI in M23-M24, and several preparatory materials were prepared, such as PowerPoint presentations, an interactive virtual exercise, messages for social media, registration form, etc. The workshop had also external invitees and gathered 16 participants (and a total of 32 persons registered). By building on this experience, US together with UK partners worked together on improving the overall engagement strategy, by trying to find more effective event formats in order to achieve all the envisioned results from this activity. A virtual interactive tool was provided by PP6 US to UK partners in order to collaborate on this.

The second workshop in the UK was organized as part of the Cereals event (8-9 June 2022). As the workshop took place in an open field with limited access to the internet, Urbasofia has prepared a survey available also offline, which included dedicated questions for farmers, AD operators and the wider audience. The answers to the survey were collected and a statistic analysis has been conducted for their interpretation. The workshop was a success and captured the interest of a variety of relevant stakeholders such as farmers, AD operators, consultants and fertilizer companies (present in a high number). The discussions were mainly held with arable farmers, but an additional important topic was the fertilizers' cost and value for money, which was perceived more important than sustainability/soil health aspects. The discussions with farmers also brought to light many relevant issues which were not considered by the NOMAD team before, so the event was considered a success also from this point of view, of expanding the knowledge. The team also had more technical discussions about carbon savings certification schemes with several companies, which considered the NOMAD product a potential method to reduce the carbon emissions in farming practices in the future.

The last workshop organized in the UK was merged with the final NOMAD event and was organized at UCL premises. Speakers from Greece and UK have presented current state, challenges and emerging technologies of the digestate market. A panel discussion with experts took place to share their experiences and thoughts on digestate valorisation and policy makers. More than 30 persons were present at the workshop, representing Biogas operators, farming associations, the policy and the scientific environment.

Figure 17 - Left: CEREALS 2022 (Cambridgeshire, UK); right: final NOMAD conference (London, UK)

Stakeholder Engagement in Greece

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

Greece has also organized the first 2 workshops in 2022. The first one as part of the Climate Neutral Week was held on the 1st of June 2022 in the Greek city of Kozani. The most important activity within the workshop was the presentation of the trailer #2 and its functions to the audience virtually, by the lead partner. They have described the work currently done on the trailer to take its final form before the field trial begins, and several technical discussions about this topic followed. The participants stressed the relevance of this product for the proper management of waste, with a specific case presentation from a biogas unit owner in the area, who highlighted the importance of the unit for its own ones. Furthermore, apart from the technical discussions, the viability of funding for operating such units in Western Macedonia has been explored, with representatives of farmers associations showing particular interest in the product.

The second one was part of the Agrotica Fair in Thessaloniki (20-23 October), where the greek partners took the opportunity of presenting trailer #2 to the participants. Additionally, the LP held a presentation on “Innovative Techniques for the Utilization of Agricultural Residues and Wastes” and engaged the participants in a conversation on NOMAD project, while also offering them the possibility to take a look inside the trailer #2 and learn more about it.

Last but not least, the Greek partners attended the Western Macedonia Innovation Days in Kozani between 7-9 February 2023, where NOMAD results were presented to the participants.

Figure 18 - Photos of NOMAD at Agrotica Fair (Thessaloniki, Greece)

Stakeholder Engagement in Malta

The first Stakeholder Engagement Event held in Malta was within the AgriFair 2022 (20-22 May). This national event, organized by the Maltese Ministry of Agriculture, Food, Fisheries and Animal Rights, was held at the MFCC in Ta' Qali and was the first of its kind. Atriga had an exhibition of the NOMAD project in the agriculture sector, engaging with key Maltese policy makers during the event. Due to facing difficulties in bringing all the relevant stakeholders (especially policy makers) at the same table, the Maltese partners have opted for one-to-one meetings with each policy maker (as stakeholder engagement practice), in order to discuss in detail about the product and its perspectives for the future.

Figure 19 – Photos from AgriFair 2022

Stakeholder Engagement in Italy

The first stakeholder engagement event organized in Italy was the annual TRAINING CAMP 2021 event organized by ANCI Lazio in Ventotene in M24, where the synergy between two strategic and complementary European projects in which ANCI Lazio is a partner was highlighted: the DYDAS - DYnamic Data Analytics Services project (co-financed by the European program Connecting Europe Facility CEF) and by the NOMAD - Novel Organic recovery using Mobile ADvanced technology project. The 2nd edition of the "Training Camp represented an important opportunity for the local administrators of the Lazio Region since this initiative aims to broaden the horizons of knowledge on European programming and to encourage the dissemination of good practices and innovation for the management of local and to promote active citizenship. In particular, among the projects capable of generating valuable data for the agricultural sector, in which ANCI Lazio is a partner, the NOMAD project – Novel Organic recovery using Mobile ADvanced technology (co-financed by the European program HORIZON 2020) was illustrated for which the work to improve the physical qualities of the land can create an important synergy with the DYDAS project, which operates, however, to facilitate the analysis of large amounts of data.

The Italian partners have fulfilled their second stakeholder engagement activity by participating at the 'Festival of creative recycling - RiscArti Festival #10' (Rome, 6-16 April 2023). Within this event, a press conference was held on the 6th of April, presenting the NOMAD project and its innovative approach. Furthermore, an on-going info-desk was present at the festival for the whole period, and the Italian partners were available for answering to questions related to NOMAD and also offered communication materials to the participants. Moreover, the partners had a presentation on the NOMAD results (followed by an interactive session) on the 14th of April.

Last but not least, the NOMAD project results were presented last June 9th 2023 in a webinar titled "Recovery of NOMAD nutrients and HOOP bioeconomy" organised by ANCI Lazio under the EU GREEN WEEK (3 June - 11 June 2023), an initiative dedicated to promoting and deepening European environmental policies. In particular, the partners from ANCI Lazio and the University of Florence, illustrated the results of the European NOMAD project for the use of innovative fertilizers in agriculture obtained through an experiment conducted in Lazio through the NOMAD-mobile unit which allowed the recovery of water, fibres and specific nutrients from the digestate. They have also

presented the tests carried out in Italy with the organic fertilizer produced through the NOMAD process and developing tests in a controlled environment (in a greenhouse) for the growth of a variety of lettuce.

Figure 20 - Photos of press conference at 'Festival of creative recycling - RiscArti Festival #10' (Rome, Italy)

6. Online outreach

6.1. Website

The NOMAD website (<http://www.projectnomad.eu>) in English went online in M5, the version in Mandarin went online in M6 (Figure 21). During the lifetime of the project, the website was filled with more content (i.e., news article), information was updated to reflect current developments and new sections (i.e., 'Media centre') were added.

Figure 21 - NOMAD website landing page; English (left) and Mandarin (right)

In total, our website received 16028 visits, with an average visit duration of 1 minute and 35 seconds. On average, visitors performed 2.2 actions per visit. Our website exceeded the goal of 2000 visits per year with an average of 2509 visits.

Analysis of the distribution of page visits showed that the homepage is the most visited page with 50% of total visits. This is followed by the "Project" page with 11% of visits and the "Field Trials" page with 7% of visits. The "NOMAD trailer(s)" page accounts for 6% of visits. These numbers illustrate the areas of our website that are of particular interest to our audience.

Over time, we have observed an interesting trend in visitor behaviour. Initially, the number of visits and page views were higher, but engagement was relatively low. Over time, the

D7.10 Final Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Monitoring

number of somewhat visits decreased, but the quality of individual visits improved. Visitors spent more time on the site, and the number of actions and downloads increased significantly. This indicates that we were successful in capturing the attention and interest of our audience, which ultimately leads to a more engaged user base.

Our target countries of Greece, Italy, Malta and the UK are among the top 10 countries with the most website visitors, so local communication at the demo sites worked. Overall, our audience is predominantly European (Figure 22).

Figure 22 - NOMAD website visitors by country

Analysis of the sources of our website traffic shows that the majority of visits, 60%, come from search engine listings. This indicates that our website is effectively optimized for search engines so that users can easily find our content. In addition, 35% of visits come from direct entries, indicating that users are familiar with our website and frequently visit it directly.

6.2. Social Networks

In M1 a Twitter and LinkedIn channel for NOMAD were established. The accounts are used to promote the project and stay in touch with specific target groups.

Although we have not reached the targeted 200 fans on LinkedIn, we currently have a solid base of 159 fans. The majority of our fans are based in Europe, with a significant presence in Greece and the UK. It is worth noting that most of our fans on LinkedIn work in the research services, indicating a relevant and interested audience. Similar to LinkedIn, we have not reached our goal of 500 fans on Twitter, we currently have 282 fans. However, our engagement rate on both LinkedIn (3% average) and Twitter (4.5%) is quite good and indicates that our existing fan base is actively interacting with our content, and we are reaching our target audiences. Even with this smaller fan base, we were still able to connect, distribute our content, and achieve positive results.

Figure 23 - Screenshots of Twitter (top) and LinkedIn (bottom) channel

7. Outreach in China

Part of NOMAD was a non-European cooperation with Chinese partners of the IUE (Institute of urban environment, China Academy of Science). The cooperation was such that there was a separate NOMAD project on both sides (Europe & China), which is not 1 to 1 identical, but dealt with the same topic (digestate processing, fertilizer production and water recovery) and processes.

The main objective of the cooperation was the exchange of knowledge and findings on the subject. The Chinese NOMAD project did not build mobile trailers for biogas plants, but a plant for the treatment of municipal wastewater (public toilets). Nitrogen and phosphorus were extracted by SED, as in Europe, and additionally with modified biochar. Fertilizer was then produced from the extracted nutrients. In addition, digestate from food waste was treated in various ways (e.g. aerobic composting, anaerobic composting, biochar admixing). The results were tested in field trials for fertilizer performance.

Lessons learned are shared internally among the NOMAD partners and the following lists the communication & dissemination actions on the Chinese side for their project parts.

7.1. Event participation

The Chinese partners participate in two large events communicating their NOMAD results. They communicated with many experts and business representatives the complete equipment for preparation of biochar from sludge by hydrothermal dehydration coupled with pyrolysis and the relevant contents of NOMAD. The knowledge of NOMAD was disseminated to the public in the form of exhibitions and posters.

Table 9 - Overview of events in China

Date	Title	Location
M14	National kitchen waste Recycling Technology Conference	Xiamen Island
M15	2 nd Xiamen International Environmental Protection Industry Innovation Technology Exhibition	Xiamen Island

Figure 24 - Photos of event participation of Chinese partners

7.2. Event hosting

While the field trials of the second part of the project (Digestate from Foodwaste as Fertilizer) were underway, faculty and students from Jimei University, as well as the local community were able to visit them to understand the resource use of food waste compost.

Figure 25 - Photos of field trials in China including visits from students and local community

7.3. News outreach

There was a news report about the Chinese NOMAD project and field trials on Jimei TV Xiamen in July 2021.

7.4. Digital Media

A public WeChat account has been created under the name CAS-IUE-UECRG to publish NOMAD results (which runs under the account of IUE, CAS). The latest results of NOMAD can be quickly viewed by the public in the future through this account.

7.5. Brochure

A printed brochure and a digital brochure with the final results were created. The digital brochure can be accessed under the following QR-code (Figure 26).

Figure 26 – Left: Printed Chinese NOMAD brochure; Right: QR-code to access Chinese NOMAD brochure

7.6. Stakeholder Engagement

Experts from the Ministry of Housing and Rural Development in the fields of waste classification and solid waste recycling were invited, to visit the field trials and exchange views on the subject of the project.

Figure 27 - Visit of Chinese Ministry of Housing and Rural Development of Chinese field trial site

7.7. Dissemination – scientific publication

Several open access and non-open access scientific publications have been published by the Chinese partners on NOMAD relevant topics from the results of the project. An overview of reference, link and information on open access can be found in table 9.

Table 10 - Overview of scientific publications of Chinese NOMAD partners

Reference	Open Access?
Fang X.J., Gao B., Zhong D.L., Cui S.H. et al.; Closing the food waste loop: Analysis the agronomic performance and potential of food waste disposal products; JCLP; 2023, 382	NO
Ba D., Qimei D., Zhao W. et al.; Patterns of microbial communities were shaped by bioavailable P along elevation gradient of Shergyla Mountains, as determined by analysis of phospholipid acids; PloS one, 2022, 17(7)	YES
Wang L., Huang W., Zhao C., Cui S.H. et al; Exploring the environment-nutrition-obesity effects associated with food consumption in different groups in China; Journal of Environmental Management; 2022, 317	NO
Wang Y., Yu G.W., Lin J.Y. et al; Synergistic hydrothermal treatment of food waste digestate residue and incineration fly ash: dehydration performance and heavy metals safety; Reaction Chemistry & Engineering 7(8), 1797-1806	NO
Cai G., Ye Z.L.; Cncentration-dependent adsorption behaviours and machanisms for ammonium and phosphate removal by optimized MG-impregnated biochar; Journal of Cleaner Production; 2022,349	NO
Huang Y.F., Zhao C., Gao B., Cui S.H. et al; Life cycle assessment and society willingness to pay indexes of food waste-to-energy strategies; Journal of Environmental Management; 2022, 305	NO
Huang Y.F., Gao B., Cui S.H. et al; Producing more potatoes with less inputs and greenhouse gases emissions by regionalized cooperation in China; Journal of Cleaner Production; 2021, 299	NO
Zhao C., Gao B., Wang L., Cui S.H. et al; Spatial patterns of net greenhouse gas balance and intensity in Chinese orchard systems; Science of the Total Environment; 2021, 779	NO
Shakoor M.B., Ye Z.L., Chen S.H.; Engineered biochars for recovering phosphate and ammonium from wastewater: A review; Science of the Total Environment; 2021, 779	NO
Zhong Q., Wang L., Cui S.H.; Urban food systems: a bibliometric review from 1991 to 2020; Foods; 2021, 10(3)	YES

8. Conclusion

In summary, it was challenging for our project to achieve certain key performance indicators (KPIs), such as the number of followers on social media, the number of peer-reviewed publications, and the final number of conference attendees. However, we are confident that we still effectively reached our target audience and conveyed the essence of our project, prioritizing quality over quantity.

The impact of COVID-19 and the Ukraine war significantly delayed the development and testing of our trailers, which in turn impacted KPIs for reporting results and, for example, events related to our trailers. Nevertheless, we proactively sought alternative solutions to overcome these obstacles. Given the time constraints, we opted to participate in larger external issue-related events rather than organize our own event to ensure that our message was still disseminated to our target audience. And when there was an international travel ban because of COVID-19, we solved the impossibility of shooting live-action film by producing our introductory video as an animated film.

Despite these challenges, we were able to achieve several key metrics, such as the number of website visits per year, the number of journalistic articles and videos published, and active participation in various events and conferences. By holding additional smaller events with local stakeholders in each country, we were able to reach a more targeted audience than the broader audience we reached with videos and articles, for example.

To address the different audiences, we chose a communication strategy that used a combination of local languages and English. This approach facilitated effective communication and improved our ability to appeal to different segments of our target audience.

It is important that our website, videos, and some online publications remain accessible after the project is complete. This means that interested parties can continue to access information and be inspired. The continued availability of these resources will ensure that the impact of our project extends beyond the original timeframe.

